

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/376788005>

Navigating China's Security Paradigm

Article · November 2023

CITATIONS

0

READS

47

2 authors:

[Keshav Mishra](#)

Banaras Hindu University

2 PUBLICATIONS 0 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

[Rishabh Verma](#)

Banaras Hindu University

9 PUBLICATIONS 0 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

ISSN 0970-7247

THIRD CONCEPT

Vol. 37

No. 441

NOVEMBER 2023

Rs. 550.00

- ❖ **Conflicts & Resolution in Northeast**
- ❖ **Military & Political Institutions of Myanmar**
- ❖ **Zero-Carbon Transition through Green Technologies**
- ❖ **Unrealized and Unregulated Arena of Bio-warfare**
- ❖ **Comparative Analysis of Nuclear Diplomacy**
- ❖ **India's Marital Rape Crisis**
- ❖ **Climate Change Impact on Human Security in South Asia**
- ❖ **Key to Achieving SDG-4 & NEP 2020**

Special Issue on “Security, Identity and Global Governance: India and the World”,

HIGH QUALITY
PRECISION PARTS
THAT WILL PUT YOU IN
TOP GEAR

Perfection requires an ideal blend of men & machines. That is what has made us a renowned name in the field of precision components, with manufacturing facilities that have won the ISO-9002 and QS-9000 certifications.

We have the capability to develop and produce to your specifications and are in a position to even create a dedicated manufacturing line for large volumes at short notice.

We have High Supplier ratings from all our clients and have the distinction of being a consistent zero defect supplier to the world's largest business enterprise- General Motors, USA.

So if you are looking for precision automotive components get in touch with us. We offer a variety of Precision Turned, Milled, Drilled jobs and stampings on Swiss & German Plants with inhouse designing, tooling, surface and heat treatment.

Product Range
Automotive Transmission Parts, Carburetor Parts, Fuel Injection Equipment and Parts, Instrumentation and Engineering Goods.

Our Major Clients

- General Motors USA & France
- Simell-Switzerland, China & Hong Kong
- CIL- Hong Kong & China
- Bosch & Lomb
- Escorts Yamaha
- Ucal Mikuni

IST LIMITED

A-23, New Office Complex, Defence Colony, New Delhi-110024 (India)
Phones : 91-11-4694291, 4694292, 4617310, 4632287 Fax : 91-11-4625694
E-mail : istgroup@nda.vsnl.net.in
Website : <http://www.istindia.com>

PROJECT 10/01/08

EDITORIAL BOARD

Y.C. Simhadri, Professor (Retd),	Vice-Chancellor, Banaras Hindu University, Andhra University, Nagarjuna University, Patna University (Two Terms), Member, University Grants Commission Consultant, United Nations University, Tokyo, UNESCO, Thailand Director, Institute of Constitutional and Parliamentary Studies ICPS.
Dr. Vijay Kumar Verma	Associate Professor, Department of Political Science, Dyal Singh College, Delhi University, New Delhi.
Eddie J. Girdner, (Retired Professor)	Izmir University, Izmir, Turkey.
Dr. Kalim Siddiqui,	Teaches International Economy, Department of Accounting, Finance, and Economics, The Business School, University of Huddersfield, Queensgate, Huddersfield, UK.
Dr. Ramesh Makwana	Professor and Head Dept of Sociology, Sardar Patel University, Vallabh Vidyanagar Anand, Gujarat.
Vikram Soni, Professor (Retd),	Jamia Millia Islamia, Centre for Theoretical Physics, New Delhi.
Dr. Sabahudin Hadzialic, Professor,	Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina.
Dr. Hab. Dorota Siemieniecka, Prof. NCU	V-ce Dean for Research and International Cooperation Faculty of Education, Nicolaus Copernicus University, Toruń, Poland.
Dr. Swaleha Sindhi,	Vice President Indian Ocean Comparative Education Society (IOCES) Vadodara-Gujarat.
Dr. Ritu Sapra, Associate Professor	Department of Commerce, Delhi School of Economics, Delhi University, Delhi.
Dr. Anilkumar B. Halu	Dean and Deputy Controller of Exam HoD & PG Coordinator UG & PG Dept of Political Science Govt. College, (Autonomous), Kalaburagi,
Dr. Dipen Saikia	Principal, Moridhal College, Moridhal, Dist. Dhemaji, Assam.
Dr. Alok Kumar Gupta, Associate Professor	Department of Politics and International Relations, Central University of Jharkhand.
Nisar Ahmed I Mulla, Professor,	Head, Department of Commerce, Maulana Azad National Urdu University, Hyderabad.
Dr. Jaikishan Thakur, Associate Professor	Department of Sociology and Research Guide Govt. 1st Grade College Mahagaon, Karnataka.

An International Journal of Ideas

Vol. 37 No. 441 NOVEMBER 2023 Rs. 550. 00

Third Concept aims at providing a platform where a meaningful exchange of ideas can take place among the people of the Third World. The attempt will be to communicate, debate and disseminate information, ideas and alternatives for the resolution of the common problems facing humankind. We welcome contributions from academics, journalists and even from those who may never have published anything before. The only requirement is a concern for and desire to understand and take the issue of our time. Contributions may be descriptive, analytical or theoretical. They may be in the form of original articles, reactions to previous contributions, or even a comment on a prevailing situation. All contributions, neatly typed in double space, may be addressed to:

Babuddin Khan Editor, Manoj K. Narula Deputy Editor, Nandini Basistha Guest Editor, R.S.Rawat Business Executive, Shatrughan Kumar Dwivedi South-east Asia, M. L. Sharma Consulting Editor, R. Prudhvi Raju Managing Editor, Purba Roy Art Director

While the Editor accepts responsibility for the selection of materials to be published, individual authors are responsible for the facts, figures, and views in their articles. However, the Editor reserves the right to edit the articles for reasons of space and clarity.

Published, Printed and Owned by Babuddin Khan Third Concept, LB - 39, Prakash Deep Building, 7, Tolstoy Marg, New Delhi-110 001. Ph : 23711092, 23712249, Fax No: 23711092. E-mail : third.concept@rediffmail.com Website: www.thirdconceptjournal.co.in

THIRD CONCEPT NOW UGC-CARE List

Designed by: Pt. Tejpal

INSIDE

Editorial, Guest Editorial Message 6, Dr. Nandini Basistha, Transformational or Negotiatory: 7, Dr. Nandini Basistha, Between the Lines of Constitution:..... 12, Dr. Aynul Islam, Dr. Bibhuti Bhusan Biswas & Abu Salah Md. Yousuf, Food and Child Security in India: 16, Dr. Kaluram B. Dhore, India-China and Pakistan: Tripartite.....22, Navcharan Singh Sidhu, Micro-credentialing on the Block Chain:...27, Ms. Jyotsna & Dr. Manisha Manchanda, The Framework of the Zero-Carbon..... 32, Renuka Shyam Narai, Securing Future: Child Protection..... 38, Saket Bihar, E-governance in India: An Analytical..... 43, Dr. Dipankar Dey & Dr. Bibhuti Bhusan Biswas, Challenges & Remedial Measures.....48, Dr. Kaluram B. Dhore, Common Welfare Schemes benefiting.....53, Tripti Sharma, The Unrealized and Not So Regulated.....60, Dr. Soham Samajpaty, Iran's Nuclear Journey: A Comparative.....65, Sarabjit Kaur, Prof. (Dr.) Nagalaxmi M. Raman & Dr. Amit Kumar Mishra, Nuclear Diplomacy: Dynamics..... 70, Sarabjit Kaur, Prof. (Dr.) Nagalaxmi M. Raman & Dr. Amit Kumar Mishra, Providing Infertility Care Worldwide:.....75, Sumana Das, Sustainable Development Goal 2: Zero.....80, Arpita Singh, China's Polar Silk Road and Arctic..... 85, Riva Panchal, Cyber-feminism and its Role..... 91, Dr. Somdatta Banerjee

Scenario of Mental Health among Elderly....96	Socio-Consternation and Security Crisis..... 192
<i>Dr. Rajkumari Meena</i>	<i>Ranjini. G & Dr. Ramana Devika</i>
Changing Role of China in Contemporary.. 101	Supporting the Health of Middle..... 196
<i>Aqib Abid Mulla</i>	<i>Hameeda Begum Safavi</i>
Television Purchase: Measuring t..... 107	<i>& Dr. Sandhya Kumari</i>
<i>Subhajit Basu Chowdhury, Rupa Paul Lodh,</i>	Sports and Identity: Change and Continuity...202
<i>Swati Pal & Pritha Ghosh</i>	<i>Nutan Marian Tigga</i>
Climate Change: Impact on Human..... 112	Harmony between Human and Nature: 206
<i>Dr. Dipankar Dey</i>	<i>Dr. Laxmi Dixit & Amit Krishna</i>
Exploration of Colour Association..... 118	Portrayal of Women in Cinema:..... 210
<i>Dharani G Sekaran & Dr. Aiswarya V R</i>	<i>Priyanka Marwaha & Dr. Nancy Paul</i>
Deconstructing the Voice of Survivors..... 124	An Overview ofSDGs under India's G20.... 214
<i>Prof. Shiladitya Chakraborty & Bijetri Pathak</i>	<i>Namrata Tomar & Ayush Kumar Shukla</i>
Academic Stress and Eating Habits:..... 128	Navigating China's New Security 218
<i>Basit Javeed Qureshi & Imran Ahmad Khan</i>	<i>Prof. Keshav Mishra & Rishabh Verma</i>
India's Marital Rape Crisis: A Critical..... 138	Changing Dimensions of India - Eastern.....222
<i>Dr. Amrita Banerjee</i>	<i>Dr. Nandini Basistha & Dr. Radha</i>
Non-Traditional Security: A Critical..... 143	<i>Raghuramapatruni</i>
<i>Dr. Mousumi Das</i>	Creativity in a Standardised Curriculum:.....227
Evolving Identity of Women: A Study..... 147	<i>Kiruthiga M P & Deepak S</i>
<i>Mukta Chaturvedi</i>	Analyzing Artificial Intelligence (AI).....232
Human Security and the Role of Tribal..... 151	<i>Poulomi Mondal</i>
<i>Sharmita Ghosh</i>	Glorious Past and Promising Future: 237
Securitisation of Mobility: Migration..... 155	<i>Dr. Radha Raghuramapatruni, Reddy Venkata</i>
<i>Rejitha. R. S</i>	<i>Surya Chaintanya, & Mrs. Puspa Kumari</i>
Identity Politics: An Analysis..... 161	Constitutionality of Sedition Law..... 241
<i>Dr. Nibedita Roy & Sharif Noorjahan</i>	<i>Dr. Pooja Gupta, Dr. Sarvesh Soni</i>
Refugee's Crisis and Women's Security..... 166	<i>& Girish Pal</i>
<i>Gayathri Pramod Panamoottil</i>	Bitcoin Privacy and Security: Assessing.... 245
Public Perception and Attitude: Skill..... 171	<i>Ms. Dixita R. Suthar</i>
<i>Dr. Boby Narayan</i>	<i>& Dr. Kiran C. Bharatiya</i>
Unravelling the Identity Crisis of Madhesis...178	Data Privacy Challenges in Digital..... 249
<i>Dr. Priyadarshini Purohit & Sakshi Rathi</i>	<i>Swati Tyagi & Dr. Priya Dhingra</i>
Indigenous Knowledge for Crisis..... 184	Socio-Cultural, Economic and Sustainable...256
<i>Dr. Laxmiram Gope & Sujit Kuiry</i>	<i>Neha Pawar Singh</i>
Ninth Schedule and Judicial Review 188	India's Quest for Self-Reliance..... 264
<i>Dr. Mamta Mishra, Dr. Samidha Singh &</i>	<i>Alok Kumar Gupta & Kaushiki Parihar</i>
<i>Bhartendu Chaudhary</i>	

Navigating China's New Security Paradigm: Exploring BRI, Made in China 2025 and the Question of Hegemony

Prof. Keshav Mishra* & Rishabh Verma**

National security walks hand in hand with the identity of the nation. The policies are framed on the basis of the inherent nature of the state but in the peculiar case of the Chinese Identity the question of 'Who' has been a constant prefix. E. J. Hobsbawm among several others has tried to define the national identity and various facets of it, he particularly states that it is not a primary nor an unchanging social entity, it therefore belongs to a particular period. It further relates to the certain kind of definition to the modern nation-state thus, he finds that it is pointless to discuss nation and its identity except in so far as both relate to it.¹ Omar Dahbour argues that, "the 'antecedent affinities' of national groups can be characterized as identities that are ascribed to individuals, rather than common practices or ideas that might serve as the basis for association."²

The following article attempts to deduce the new strategic narratives on the background of their construction of the national identity and its evolving security landscapes and partnerships. Further critically examining their projects with respect to the accusations of the hegemonic rise of China and its impact on the regions of Southeast Asia and South Asia with respect to India and the Global South.

Historical development of the Chinese identity

China's identity has been shaped by the external challenges and internal dynamics. Historically, they saw themselves as the "Middle Kingdom" and were mainly following the policy of isolationism while focusing on their own internal development. They suffered from what was the so-called Middle kingdom complex and their Sino centric view predicated the rest of the world as "all under heaven". In the Odes³ it states that, "under the wide heaven, there is no land that is not the emperor's"⁴ This Sino centric syndrome was the embodiment of country's great power status that it still strives to regain.

This sense of centrality was shaken when China was forced to open its doors for the foreign powers who were more technologically advanced and equipped with modern artillery dominated and humiliated China destroying their pride of being the heaven. Xi on the CCP's hundredth anniversary spoke about the humiliation stating that "gradually reduced by foreign powers to a semi-colonial, semi-feudal society that was wrecked and was subjected to an intense humiliation for the whole nation, bringing great pain to its people and the Chinese civilization was plunged into the darkness."⁵ This period taught the Chinese how the strong treat the weaker ones and was an important lesson that same pain can again be inflicted upon them if they grow weak again.⁶

Mao Zedong was fundamental in reviving the great power identity among the common masses of China as the formation of PRC in 1949 was the first incident since 1911 that all the country's resources were at disposal of a single person. The speech made on 21st September 1949 titled, "The Chinese People Have Stood Up"⁷ was his assertion that China will in future emerge as a nation with developed culture, military and economy remarking that the future of PRC was "Infinitely Bright"⁸. This brought forward the ideology of laying low and hiding your potential which remained active in the practices of CCP and PRC. Keeping a Low Profile (KLP)

* Dept of History, Faculty of Social Science, Banaras Hindu University.

** Research Scholar, Dept of History, Faculty of Social Science, Banaras Hindu University, Uttar Pradesh.

became the standard tactic for PRC in international relations and strategic narratives. It had strong support among the Chinese scholars and diplomats. The main theme of the KLP was reiterated by Deng Xiaoping in 1990 when he states that, “We should continue to observe the international situation. There are contradictions that we can use, conditions that are favourable to us, opportunities that we can take advantage of — the problem is to seize them at the right moment.”⁹ When the talks of adapting a new strategy resumed the veteran diplomats of China argued that time was still not right to deter from the policy that had been at the foundation of Chinese Foreign Policy and must be kept for another hundred years as they were not developed enough and still has a long way to go.¹⁰ The strategy was influential in the peaceful rise as they repeatedly emphasized not challenging America for the global leadership to help them continue their trajectory of development also misdirecting the United States from planning a countermeasure against them. The repeated phrases of ‘no expansion’ and ‘no hegemony’ were used to indicate that the others should not fear them also playing the charade of a responsible power. The Hu Jintao’s administration tried to erase the negative connotations surrounding the KLP by projecting and adopting the term of ‘being moderate and cautious.’¹¹

The coming of Xi Jinping at the helm of Chinese politics completely altered the Chinese identity and the trajectory of the global politics. He envisioned ‘the great Chinese Rejuvenation’ and made efforts to reclaim the ancient glories of the country. The question of Chinese identity the Chinese scholars tend to agree that it does not have a fixed identity instead it is a state that is governed by several competing ideas and narratives.¹² As Henry Kissinger puts it, “China does not see itself as a rising, but a returning power.... It does not view the prospect of a strong China exercising influence in economic, cultural, political, and military affairs as an unnatural challenge to world order—but rather as a return to a normal state of affairs.”¹³

The Idea of Xi and the Hegemonic expansion of China

The coming of Xi Jinping into power brought an end to the era of pragmatism and non-ideological governance. His thought represents the ideas and values that have been enshrined in the CCP’s constitution. It is his adaptation of the Marxist-Leninist philosophy which was set aside by his predecessors. He reasserted his influence over every sector of the public policy and private life. The wave of nationalism increased with him following an increasingly assertive foreign policy that is termed as ‘Striving for Achievement (SFA)’.¹⁴ The 19th party Congress in 2017 he initiated ambitious projects that were CCP’s ‘historic mission’ in the new era but more importantly were his foreign policy and security goals in which he envisioned the “dream of building a powerful military” and the adaptation of “one country, two systems” and ensuring its complete jurisdiction over the regions of Hong Kong and Macao. Furthermore, the objectives of ensuring China’s dominant role in the reformation and development of global governance system and to incorporate the Chinese wisdom and strength in it.¹⁵

The development policies like Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) and Made in China 2025 were the major takeaways from the speech which indicated his hegemonic aspirations, a dream that has been long pursued by the Chinese leadership. Domestically, he consolidated his power by eliminating his rivals within the CCP and constitutional changes that would allow him to exercise his power indefinitely. The framework that emerging conventional wisdom came up with was that China will try to establish the global influence by first achieving regional hegemony.¹⁶ Although Xi on various occasions has refrained from publicly accepting the hegemonic aspirations.¹⁷ But the territorial assertiveness shown by the Chinese whether it would be establishing its de facto control in the South China Sea or violating the ‘9th dash line’ portray it otherwise.¹⁸ The imperial map released by China on 28th August 2023 is another part of its mind games while it acts as a wolf in a sheep’s clothing. The new map violates the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) thus violating the economic zones of many Southeast Asian countries. It also claims its legitimacy over the Indian regions of Arunachal Pradesh and Aksai chin while encroaching the Russian territory.¹⁹

Changing Security Paradigms and its impact on India and the Global South

China's national security is an embodiment of the economic, technological & political elements along with an outlook towards defence.²⁰ China began to develop a new concept of security since the collapse of the Soviet Union. This became their primary modus operandi in altering the position of US in the regions of East Asia and South east Asia.²¹ Under Xi the concept has been further expanded encompassing all the development goals under the national security with the eventual goal of protecting the interests and stability of the nation for the coming years. This new stature of the CCP leaves behind the traces of the old defensive approach and supports the forceful pre-emptive measures towards the perceived threats controlling the China related narratives.²² Measures have also been prepared to any challenges that can occur in the country protecting its interests internally and externally to ensure the long-term survival of the model state.²³

China's desire to reshape global maps, beyond just the Indo-Pacific region, has driven it to seek an alternative global order, leveraging its economic influence. Xi Jinping has formed alliances with nations like Iran and Pakistan, sharing China's discontent with the current world order. These alliances have two main goals: undermining the existing system and weakening China's key rivals – the United States, India, and Japan. China, recognizing India's potential as a counterbalance in Asia due to its population and growing economy, sought to limit its influence by strengthening ties with Pakistan. Additionally, China expanded its strategic reach by partnering with Iran and Russia, while also deepening economic cooperation with Israel.²⁴

Conclusion

Under the leadership of Xi Jinping, China's evolving identity and security strategies have had significant global implications, particularly in Southeast Asia, South Asia, and the Global South. China's historical identity as the "Middle Kingdom" and its desire to regain its former status as a major power have played a crucial role in shaping its current foreign policy. While Mao Zedong initiated China's assertiveness on the world stage, Xi Jinping has ushered in a more ambitious foreign policy, deviating from the previous "Keeping a Low Profile" approach. Xi's vision for "rejuvenation" and the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) reflects China's aspirations for hegemony. China's evolving security concept encompasses economic and technological elements, aimed at protecting its interests both domestically and internationally. This approach has led to concerns, especially in the Indo-Pacific region, where China's aggressive actions and engagement with neighbouring countries have sparked tensions, particularly with India. The aftermath of the Covid-19 pandemic has intensified global scrutiny of China's actions, raising concerns about its handling of the situation and potential marginalization. India is actively seeking cooperation with other nations to address the perceived threat posed by China. China's involvement in Africa is also evolving as it increasingly focuses on providing security in addition to pursuing its interests. Understanding China's changing national identity and strategic goals is crucial for shaping future international relations. Balancing China's rise and managing its assertiveness is essential for maintaining stability and peace in the Asia-Pacific region and beyond. However, the world must also be cautious of the "Kindleberger Trap," ensuring that China, as a rising global power, behaves responsibly and provides global public goods. China's actions on the global stage continue to draw close scrutiny, echoing the idea that "the possession of great power necessarily implies great responsibility."

Endnotes

1. Hobsbawm, E. J. (1991). *Nations and Nationalism since 1780*. Cambridge University Press. page. 9-10.
2. ahbour, Omar (2002). "National Identity: An Argument for the Strict Definition." *Public Affairs Quarterly* 16, no. 1: 17-37, page. 30. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/40441311>
3. Shi Jing (The Book of Odes) is the earliest collection of Chinese poetry, and was originally called Shi (Poems), containing 305 poems from the Western Zhou Dynasty (11th century-771BC) to the mid

Spring and Autumn Period (770-476BC) and including three sections, namely, Feng (songs), Ya (odes) and Song (hymns).

4. Hoo, T. B. (2018). *China's Global Identity: Considering the responsibilities of Great Power*. Georgetown University Press. p. 2.
5. Jinping, Xi (2021), Speech on the Communist Party of China's 100th Anniversary. http://www.xinhuanet.com/english/special/2021-07/01/c_1310038244.htm
6. Shankar, P. R. (2022, October 16). China's 'Century of humiliation' never ended. It needs a Mandela or Gandhi now. *The Print*. <https://theprint.in/opinion/chinas-century-of-humiliation-never-ended-it-needs-a-mandela-or-gandhi-now/1167776/>
7. Zedong, M. (1949, September 21). The Chinese People Have Stood Up, *Selected Works of Mao Zedong*, vol. 5. https://www.marxists.org/reference/archive/mao/selected-works/volume-5/mswv5_01.htm
8. Zedong, M. (1949, September 30). "Long Live the Great Unity of the Chinese People," in *Selected Works of Mao Zedong*, vol. 5. https://www.marxists.org/reference/archive/mao/selected-works/volume-5/mswv5_02.htm
9. *Selected Works of Deng Xiaoping (1990)*. <https://dengxiaopingworks.wordpress.com/2013/03/18/the-international-situation-and-economic-problems/>
10. Jingcai, W. & Jing, L. (2009, June 01). Wu Jianmin Describing China's Diplomacy of 60 Years: Keeping a Low Profile Should Be Guideline for 100 Years. *China News Network*. <https://www.chinanews.com.cn/gn/news/2009/06-01/1713676.shtml>
11. Yan, X. (2014). From Keeping a Low Profile to Striving for Achievement. *The Chinese Journal of International Politics*, 7(2), 153–184. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cjip/pou027>
12. Pu, X. (2017). Controversial Identity of a Rising China. *The Chinese Journal of International Politics*, 10(2), 131–149. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cjip/pox004>
13. Kissinger, H. (2012). *On China*. Penguin. Page 546
14. Kevin Rudd. (2022, October 10). The World According to Xi Jinping: What China's Ideologue in Chief Really Believes. *Asia Society*. Retrieved 14 September 2023, from <https://asiasociety.org/policy-institute/world-according-xi-jinping-what-chinas-ideologue-chief-really-believes>
15. Xi Jinping's report at 19th CPC National Congress, *Xinhua*. http://www.xinhuanet.com/english/special/2017-11/03/c_136725942.htm
16. Brands, H., Sullivan, J. (2020, May 22). China Has Two Paths To Global Domination. *Carnegie Endowment for International Peace*. Retrieved 12 September 2023, from <https://carnegieendowment.org/2020/05/22/china-has-two-paths-to-global-domination-pub-81908>
17. Lee, Y. N. (2021, April 20). Xi says China 'will never seek hegemony,' no matter how strong it becomes. *CNBC*. <https://www.cnbc.com/2021/04/20/chinese-president-xi-jinping-on-globalization-multilateral-trade.html>
18. Munro, N. (2022). China's Identity through a Historical Lens. *Journal of Advanced Military Studies*, 2022(special), 35–48. <https://doi.org/10.21140/mcu.2022SIstratcul003>
19. Saha, B., Yadav, D. (2023, September 06). Why China's imperial map is drawing criticism from neighboring nations | Explained. *India Today*. Retrieved 12 September 2023, from <https://www.indiatoday.in/world/story/chinas-imperial-map-is-drawing-criticism-from-neighboring-nations-explained-2431826-2023-09-06>
20. Matthews, R., Yan, Z. (2023, September 14). China's National Security Paradigm. <https://www.rusi.orghttps://www.rusi.org>
21. Lovell, D. W., & Thayer, C. A. (2003). China's 'New Security Concept' and Southeast Asia. In *Asia-Pacific Security: Policy challenges*. essay, ANU E Press. pp. 89–107
22. Helena Legarda. (2021, June 15). China's new international paradigm: Security first | *Merics*. <https://merics.org/en/chinas-new-international-paradigm-security-first>
23. *Xinhua* (2017). "Full text of Xi Jinping's report at 19th CPC National Congress". October 18. https://www.chinadaily.com.cn/china/19thcpcnationalcongress/2017-11/04/content_34115212.htm.
24. Dwivedi, G. (2021, November 1). China's Quest for World Dominance & Its Impact on India and the Region. *India Foundation*. <https://indiafoundation.in/articles-and-commentaries/chinas-quest-for-world-dominance-its-impact-on-india-and-the-region/>

